

Interview

Overview

Time: 1 hour

Number of sections: 3 (+ some introduction)

Goal: how the in-IDE format can be adapted to better suit students learning in it (including some AI features)

Requirements: completed a course in the JetBrains Academy Plugin not more than 1 month in advance

Detailed plan

Introduction (5 minutes)

[greetings]

[check if the connection is ok]

My name is ___, and I am a researcher at XXX, [introduce others presented]

First of all, I would like to thank you for your willingness to join our research. Just to make it clear, we are trying to learn how people use the in-IDE learning format to complete programming courses.

Have you ever participated in user studies/ interviews before?

Then you know that there are no right or wrong answers in such sessions. We are really interested in how you use IDE for education purposes and invite you to be an expert today.

Our interview will last approximately 1 hour. Also, it will be recorded, but we keep all recordings confidential. We will make anonymized summaries out of them, and once the research is over, we will delete recordings and all personal data that we gathered.

Do you have any questions? [discuss questions]

Now let me start the recording, and when it starts, I will ask for your permission to record this session one more time.

[start recording]

I would like to have your permission to record this session [get the permission]

Evaluation questions:

- What IDEs do you use for your day-to-day programming activities?
- Are you familiar with any JetBrains IDE?
- Have you ever used the JetBrains Academy plugin?

General context (10-15 minutes)

Could you tell us a bit about your educational and professional background?

Field	What is your current occupation? (Formal education degree, certification, self-taught, internships, part-time job, full-time job, etc.)
Language Proficiency	In which programming languages do you consider yourself most proficient? How did you learn this language?
Tools/courses	<p>Which JetBrains IDE do you use more often and which kind of license do you have, e.g. work, student? How long have you been using it?</p> <p>Check the participant's knowledge of the plugin: For which purposes did you use the IDE in the learning context? Have you ever tried the JetBrains Academy plugin and the in-IDE learning?</p> <p>How did you discover the JetBrains Academy plugin? Why have you decided to try it? How long have you been using the plugin? Which courses did you solve with the plugin?</p> <p>IF ANY INTEGRATIONS WERE MENTIONED: If the person solved the majority of the tasks in the IDE, we can consider this experience, otherwise try to focus on other courses</p> <p>What does the plugin change in the IDE? e.g., which panels or windows did you see? How did you find the course? How did you open the course in the IDE?</p> <p>Are you taking such courses individually or your classmates/friends too? IF YES: Do you collaborate during studying courses e.g. discussing and comparing possible solutions, explaining topics to each other? Did you share your solutions and how?</p>

Thank you for answering!

Now that we got more familiar with each other, let's proceed with the main part of our session today.

Interaction with IDE — which difficulties were in IDE?

Please, recall the last time you took the [\[last course name from the previous section\]](#) course.

- 1) Do you recall any problems while solving the course? (**AND IF YES** How did you manage this issue?)
 - a) Did you have any difficulties finding any buttons?
 - b) Did you have any difficulties finding files where you need to complete a task?
 - c) Did you have any difficulties finding the theory block in the course?
 - d) ...
- 2) IDE FEATURES - ask 1-3 main questions below
 - a) Are you familiar with debugging?

AND IF YES:

 - Did you use this feature to solve tasks from the course?
 - Could you describe the process of how you used debugging?
 - What aspects of this feature did you find most helpful?
 - Did you have any difficulties using it?
 - b) Are you familiar with refactorings?

AND IF YES:

 - Did you use this feature to solve tasks from the course?
 - Which kind of refactorings did you use?
 - Could you describe the process of how you used refactorings?
 - What aspects of this feature did you find most helpful?
 - Did you have any difficulties using them?
 - c) Are you familiar with shortcuts?

AND IF YES:

 - Did you use this feature to solve tasks from the course?
 - Which kind of shortcuts did you use?
 - Could you describe the process of how you used shortcuts?
 - What aspects of this feature did you find most helpful?
 - Did you have any difficulties with using them?
 - d) Are you familiar with code completion?

AND IF YES:

 - Did you use this feature to solve tasks from the course?
 - Could you describe the process of how you used code completion?
 - What aspects of this feature did you find most helpful?
 - Did you have any difficulties with usage?
 - Did you use full line code completion? (and for which tasks)
 - e) Did you use any other IDE features while solving the course?

IF NONE:

How do you usually overcome difficulties with incorrect answers, if any?

Now we know how you used the IDEs to solve programming courses. Let's talk about getting help during solving programming exercises.

What kind of assistant the user needs and how students trust them

- 1) How do you usually get help while learning?
 - a) Do you use a textbook/popular resources like StackOverflow/technical documentation/asking help from teachers or friends?
FOR EACH WAY:
 - b) Which type of help do you get via this resource?
 - c) How often do you need this type of help?
- 2) Have you tried any of the currently available AI-based tools - such as Chat GPT - to get any help during learning?
IF YES FOR 2-3 TOOLS:
 - a) How was your experience?
 - b) Do you continue to use it?
IF YES:
 - a) Is it now your main online help tool for this kind of tasks?
IF NO:
 - b) Why did you stop using it?
 - c) Do you trust the output of this tool?
 - i) Could you grade the level of your trust on a five points scale?
 - ii) Do you trust more the traditional way to solve this task eg [options from answer to the first question in this section]?
 - iii) Do you have a way of double-checking the AI output?
- 3) [short last question] Imagine having an AI assistant that can provide any features that you want.
 - a) Name the top three tasks you'd solve in the course [course name from the user answer]
 - a) Name the top three tasks you would NOT solve (e.g. you don't have enough trust, you prefer another source of information, etc.) and why?

Conclusion (5 minutes)

Thank you very much for all your answers and active participation.

How do you feel, is everything ok?

Do you have anything to add about the adaptation of IDEs for education purposes or about the research? I'd be grateful for any feedback.

Before we end, is there anything you would like to ask us about? [answer questions from respondent]

I'd like to clarify, if you agree to get an Amazon certificate as a prize?

Perfect, then in a couple of days, you'll receive an email from us with the link to your gift.

[say goodbye]

[stop the recording]

[short discussion with colleagues]